

Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance – The Relationship and Impact: An Exploratory Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Administrative Leaders at the Technical Management Institute of Nineveh

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the nature of the relationship and impact between smart leadership and sustainable performance in a technical educational environment through an exploratory study of the opinions of a sample of administrative leaders at the Technical Management Institute – Nineveh. The importance of the study stems from the rapid changes witnessed by educational organizations, which impose urgent needs for smart leadership styles characterized by flexibility, adaptability, and strategic decision-making that supports the sustainability of performance and the achievement of long-term goals.

The study relied on a descriptive analytical approach and was applied to a purposive sample of administrative leaders within a study population of 50 individuals, with a sample size of 30. A questionnaire was used as the main data collection tool, and the results were analyzed using SPSS version 28.

The study was based on the main hypothesis: "There is a statistically significant correlation between smart leadership and sustainable performance." The results showed a significant impact relationship between the dimensions of smart leadership (rational intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence) and sustainable performance with its three dimensions: economic, social, and environmental. The study also indicated that smart leadership contributes to supporting organizational sustainability by improving decision quality, enhancing organizational interaction, and achieving a balance between present demands and future aspirations.

In light of the results, the study presented a set of recommendations, the most prominent of which are: the importance of adopting smart leadership practices as a strategic choice and providing training programs to develop the skills of administrative leaders in support of sustainability directions in educational organizations.

Keywords: *smart leadership, sustainable performance, Technical Management Institute, Nineveh.*

JEL Classification codes: *O15, Q01.*

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Suggested citation: Ali, A.M., Mustafa, A.A., & Saeed, M.F. (2025). Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance – The Relationship and Impact: An Exploratory Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Administrative Leaders at the Technical Management Institute of Nineveh. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(4), 157-177. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2025.2(4).13

Introduction

Contemporary work environments are witnessing rapid and complex transformations driven by technological advancements, economic and social changes, and increased competitiveness at both local and global levels. This situation compels organizations of all types to adopt modern management approaches that ensure their survival and the sustainability of their performance. Within this context, the concept of smart leadership has emerged as one of the contemporary management concepts focusing on employing organizational intelligence, logical analysis, and flexibility in dealing with internal and external environmental changes to enhance performance effectiveness and achieve long-term organizational goals.

Smart leadership is not limited to possessing technical or cognitive skills; it also encompasses the ability to innovate, make data-driven decisions, and build a motivating organizational environment based on future vision and intelligent responsiveness to challenges. Consequently, the importance of studying the relationship between smart leadership practices and the concept of sustainable performance increases. Sustainable performance represents the organization's ability to achieve balanced and continuous outcomes across economic, social, and environmental levels, ensuring its stability and success in the future.

In light of this, this research aims to investigate the impact of smart leadership on achieving sustainable performance through an exploratory study of the opinions of a sample of administrative leaders (Salim, 2025) at the Technical Management Institute – Nineveh. The significance of this study lies in its contribution to providing a theoretical and practical framework that enhances educational organizations' understanding of the importance of adopting smart leadership styles that support the sustainability of their performance, especially in contexts facing significant organizational and structural challenges, as is the case in Iraqi educational organizations.

The study consists of four sections: the first covers the study methodology, while the second and third sections address the theoretical and practical aspects of the study, respectively. The study concludes with the fourth section presenting the main conclusions and recommendations.

Research Methodology

Research Problem

Educational organizations in Iraq, including the Technical Management Institute – Nineveh, face increasing challenges related to their ability to keep pace with rapid environmental and technological changes and achieve sustainable performance levels that ensure continuity and development. Adopting effective leadership approaches is considered one of the fundamental pillars to address these challenges. The concept of smart leadership has emerged as a modern approach that can effectively contribute to improving organizational performance and ensuring its sustainability through employing smart leadership methods in decision-making processes. Despite growing interest in modern leadership concepts, there remains a clear deficiency in understanding the nature of the relationship between smart leadership practices and the level of sustainable performance in educational organizations, particularly within local contexts facing complex administrative and structural challenges. Thus, the research problem stems from a

knowledge and application gap regarding the extent to which smart leadership contributes to achieving sustainable performance within the Technical Management Institute – Nineveh. This necessitates exploring the views of the administrative leadership working there and analyzing their leadership practices from the perspective of leadership intelligence and its impact on performance sustainability.

Accordingly, the research problem is encapsulated in the following main question: **What is the relationship between smart leadership and sustainable performance, and to what extent does smart leadership affect achieving sustainable performance according to a sample of administrative leadership opinions at the Nineveh Institute?**

From this main question, several sub-questions emerge:

1. What is the level of application of smart leadership principles among the institute's administrative leadership?
2. To what extent are sustainable performance indicators achieved in the work environment at the institute?
3. Is there a statistically significant relationship between smart leadership and sustainable performance?
4. To what extent do the dimensions of smart leadership contribute to explaining or predicting the level of sustainable performance?

Importance of the Research

This research aims to assist the administrative leadership at the Technical Management Institute – Nineveh in understanding the importance of applying smart leadership styles and their impact on improving the efficiency and sustainability of performance. Ultimately, this leads to the development of management methods and the enhancement of organizational work quality. Moreover, it provides data and indicators that can support administrative decision-making based on intelligence and flexibility, aligned with the requirements of sustainable development in educational organizations. The study also contributes to enriching scientific knowledge on the concepts of smart leadership and sustainable performance by examining their relationship within an Iraqi educational environment, a field that has not received sufficient research attention locally.

Research Objectives

1. To identify the level of application of smart leadership concepts and practices among the administrative leadership in the researched organization.
2. To measure the extent to which sustainable performance is achieved in the work environment within the researched organization.
3. To analyze the relationship between smart leadership and sustainable performance from the perspective of the administrative leadership.
4. To determine the impact of the dimensions of smart leadership (emotional intelligence, rational intelligence, spiritual intelligence) in enhancing sustainable performance.
5. To assess the availability of sustainable performance dimensions (environmental, social, economic) in the researched organization.
6. To provide practical recommendations to improve administrative leadership methods, positively reflecting on the sustainability of organizational performance.

Research Hypotheses

First Hypothesis:

The researched organization adopts smart leadership and sustainable performance, which implies:

- The organization adopts the smart leadership variable based on the responses and opinions of the surveyed individuals.
- The organization adopts the sustainable performance variable based on the responses and opinions of the surveyed individuals.

Second Hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant correlation between the variables of smart leadership and sustainable performance, implying:

- There is a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and sustainable performance.
- There is a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and the dimensions of sustainable performance.

Third Hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant impact of smart leadership on sustainable performance, implying:

- There is a statistically significant impact of the dimensions of smart leadership on sustainable performance.

Figure 1. The Study's Hypothetical Framework
Source: Prepared by the researchers

Theoretical Framework

Introduction to Leadership

The term leadership was historically defined through battles and wars that demonstrated the importance of the leader's personality. The first teacher and leader was and remains our Prophet

Muhammad (peace be upon him), who was distinguished by military, educational, humanitarian, and administrative leadership skills (Al-Mutairi et al., 2019, p. 6). The Prophet (peace be upon him) was an incomparable leader, and Allah Almighty described his qualities in the verse: "And We have not sent you except as a mercy to the worlds" (Quran 21:107), indicating that he was both a teacher and a leader simultaneously a trait not found in known leaders such as Napoleon or Hitler. Leadership has been defined as the process through which an individual influences a group of others to achieve goals (Sharma, 2013, p. 310). Leaders are born, not made; they carry the traits and qualities of leadership. According to Gibson et al. (2012, p. 314), leadership is an attempt to use influence to motivate and direct individuals toward achieving certain goals. From the researchers' perspective, leadership is the ability to influence, motivate, and guide individuals toward achieving common objectives. It carries the responsibility for the group to attain the desired results, as indicated by Al-Shalmah and Al-Hamad (2023, p. 195), who define leadership as the ability to influence individuals and groups working in organizations to perform tasks efficiently and effectively in order to achieve the goals of both individuals and the organization.

Concept of Smart Leadership

Smart leadership is the ability to develop and enhance competencies and skills, both personal and those of the leader, by integrating different types of intelligence and creative energies with the leader's capacity to process information in a way that adapts to both external and internal environments, facing difficulties and challenges, and making long-term decisions (Al-Karraawi, 2016, p. 37). Al-Majali (2019, p. 11) views smart leadership as a creative process characterized by forming participative and relational connections that focus on providing solutions for every intelligent and participative skill in leadership and management. Management processes include organization, planning, control, and guidance to achieve desired objectives, which are reflected in investment and development projects, and consequently in human behavior marked by innovation, capability, and knowledge that bring about positive changes. From the perspective of Salem et al. (2024, p. 28), smart leadership is a behavior naturally formed through work to generate change and foster innovation in using modern technologies to develop organizational effectiveness, based on principles of autonomy, organizational agility, responsibility, trust, and workplace thinking. Its inspiring vision combined with ethically driven behaviors helps create a shared meaning of change, leading to alignment between organizational and individual goals, values, and interests.

Based on what was previously mentioned, researchers believe that smart leadership is the leader's ability to provide solutions and adapt to any changes that occur in the internal or external environment of the organization through effective communication with employees and good management of emotions in a way that leads to achieving the goals of individuals and the organization.

The Importance of Smart Leadership

1. Paying attention to employees and striving to achieve a better future for them by involving them in decision-making processes, developing and enhancing their cognitive abilities (Al-Ghanimawi & Kazem, 2020, p. 139).
2. Serving as a link between the organization's plans and the employees to implement the required objectives, keeping pace with surrounding events and developments, and utilizing them to serve the organization to ensure survival and continuity (Al-Ghazali, 2012, p. 24).
3. The importance of smart leadership is highlighted through defining the vision, its continuity, and its implementation through the participation of work teams. This type of leadership has effectively contributed to solving problems and difficulties experienced during the industrial era, as well as addressing political, technological, economic, and other issues.

4. Smart leadership contributes to focusing on the human community, its future, and its sustainability (Al-Karraawi, 2016, p. 38). From the above, researchers believe that the importance of smart leadership emerges through the leader's interest in employees and providing them with material and moral support, in addition to striving to achieve the goals of both employees and the organization, and developing long-term strategic plans to achieve the organization's goals and ensure its sustainable continuity.

Dimensions of Smart Leadership

Many researchers have sought to describe smart leadership according to certain dimensions or knowledge areas. Both Daderman et al. (2013, p. 62) and Al-Ghanimawi & Kazem (2020, pp. 139-140) agree that the dimensions of smart leadership are as follows:

1. **Emotional Intelligence:** Refers to the ability of employees to express their emotions, understand their emotional reactions, manage themselves, and work to comprehend, motivate, and guide employees to perform tasks with high quality, effectiveness, and efficiency, enabling them to face challenges and failure with resilience.
2. **Rational Intelligence:** The leader's ability to set appropriate goals and identify suitable ways to achieve these goals according to the available resources and capabilities. This type of intelligence is acquired through surrounding situations and continuous self-learning, resulting in wise and prudent leadership (Al-Shalma & Al-Hamad, 2023, p. 203).
3. **Spiritual Intelligence:** Represents the ability to use a multi-sensory approach, including visualization, contemplation, and intuition to deeply understand the inner self in order to solve problems faced. The spiritual concept of intelligence involves elements that develop capacities and problem-solving skills. Spiritual intelligence integrates the soul and mind, contributing to enhancing an individual's adaptability by providing capabilities that assist in achieving daily goals. Researchers believe that an intelligent leader is one who is able to provide these three dimensions: spiritual intelligence, which focuses on understanding the inner depth of a person and blending the mind and spirit; emotional intelligence, which is concerned with the emotional side of working individuals; and rational intelligence, which seeks to achieve the material goals that a person seeks to achieve in order to live a free and dignified life.

Sustainable Performance

Concept of Sustainable Performance

Organizations of all types strive to achieve distinguished competitive positions to ensure their continuity and survival, especially in light of modern technological advancements, by relying on long-term strategic planning. Traditional organizations believe their success is due to achieving short-term competitive advantages that serve self-interests, whereas modern organizations manage their operations and continuity by providing benefits and services to society. Therefore, the idea of sustainable performance is manifested in the ability to face difficulties and challenges encountered by the organization, while sharing common goals and concerns about the value that sustainable business performance can achieve for society (Al-Mawajda, 2019, p. 20).

Sustainable performance refers to the organization's ability to achieve positive long-term objectives by focusing on three main dimensions called the "Sustainability Triangle," which includes the economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Sustainable performance is the performance that achieves financial efficiency and improves the quality of life within the organization and its social environment (Mansour, 2020, p. 78). It is the outcome of the economic unit's work over a period ranging from several months to a year, starting with the unit's use of available resources in an appropriate manner that results in high performance levels (Anis, 2020, p. 148).

From the perspective of Nhamo et al. (2021, p. 11), sustainable performance represents one of the most important and fundamental methods used by the economic unit to determine its level of success or failure, as well as its contribution to enhancing decision-making processes, especially strategic and critical decisions for economic units. Al-Qurashi (2017, p. 36) views sustainable performance as the process of utilizing the capabilities and skills of the economic unit to achieve the best investment of available resources, ensuring the unit's continuity and survival based on long-term strategic planning to achieve the desired goals. Likewise, Mohamed and Al-Murad (2023, p. 104) indicated that sustainable performance works to provide the necessary security, economic, and social life requirements currently and in the future without depleting natural resources through the environment and available resources, while preserving them, Researchers see, through the aforementioned, that sustainable performance is the process through which an organization seeks to focus on positive aspects and reduce the negative impacts of social, economic and environmental issues.

Importance of Sustainable Performance

Al-Mawajda (2019, p. 21), Miller et al. (2011, p. 951), agree that the importance of sustainable performance can be summarized as follows:

1. Contributing to helping economic units understand the outputs and activities they perform.
2. Facing challenges and obstacles that may hinder the achievement of the organization's goals and evaluating the extent of their implementation.
3. Sustainable performance contributes to setting standards for confronting crises and challenges.
4. It provides the organization with a comprehensive and clear vision of how the economic unit operates, its activities, the products it offers, and their impact in the present and future.
5. Reducing waste in energy and natural resource consumption, and decreasing environmental pollution to raise the community's living standards, attract the best employees, and retain them.
6. Sustainable performance contributes to lowering energy consumption, preserving natural resources, eliminating environmental pollution to achieve a healthy life, and fulfilling the objectives of both the organization and its employees (Mohamed & Al-Murad, 2023, p. 104).

Dimensions of Sustainable Performance

Bi et al. (2017, p. 18) indicate that sustainable performance consists of three dimensions known as the "three pillars of sustainability," which exist at different levels (economic, environmental, and social). All these dimensions contribute to achieving sustainability in organizations by providing decision-makers with accurate and timely information. These dimensions are as follows:

1. **Environmental Dimension:** This involves a precise description of the environment and its activities, measuring the organization's environmental commitment to protect its employees, optimize the use of available resources, reduce environmental pollution, manage waste disposal, rationalize energy consumption, minimize risks and losses, and produce safe products. It also includes achieving environmental compliance, transparency, developing employee skills, reducing product costs to align with customer affordability, and linking organizational goals with employee goals (Belhaj, 2016, p. 34).
2. **Social Dimension:** The social dimension works to balance individual productivity, economic efficiency, and society by optimally investing developed and undeveloped resources to achieve social development resulting from organizational performance. This area requires integrating social management strategies with customer needs to help organizations achieve sustainable performance and balance expectations, aspirations, needs, and stakeholders. This

enables organizations to deliver sustainable performance to customers in society by creating product value and providing services through product quality, enhanced service levels, and timely delivery, contributing to better market share and more sustainable products (Al-Mawajda, 2019, p. 24).

3. **Economic Dimension:** This dimension refers to the organization's ability to achieve financial objectives represented by gaining the trust and satisfaction of stakeholders through increased investment rates. Financial goals are among the most important foundations of this dimension, achieved over the long term. This component contributes to the organization's long-term success by comparing industry-specific competitive dimensions and their long-term effects (Al-Qurashi, 2017, p. 37), Researchers believe that sustainable performance can be achieved by focusing on three dimensions: the environmental dimension through preserving the environment, eliminating waste, and optimally utilizing environmental resources and protecting them from waste, in addition to the social dimension through providing products that benefit society and the customer, as well as the economic dimension that seeks to achieve the organization's material and profitable goals and satisfy the customer at the same time By providing high-quality products at reasonable prices and at the right time, this achieves the organization's goals and the customer's goals. Therefore, in order to achieve sustainable performance, the focus is on the three dimensions: environmental, social and economic.

Practical Aspect

Description and Diagnosis of the Research Variables

1. Smart Leadership:

a. **Rational Intelligence:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 1 (Appendix), which analyzes the indicators (X1–X5) measuring the rational intelligence dimension, that the overall indicator shows an average of 83.333% of the responses were at the levels of (Strongly Agree, Agree). In contrast, the other responses of disagreement constituted 3.33%, and neutral responses accounted for 14.666%. These responses are supported by a mean value of 4.0600 and a standard deviation of 0.682. The indicator that contributed most to enriching the positivity of this dimension was (X1).

The statement that reads "(Top management has a future vision based on the realities of its situation)" received an agreement rate of (90%). This rate is supported by a mean value of (4.233) and a standard deviation of (0.803), with a response rate of (84.666%), indicating that there are future strategies that support the vision of our esteemed university. The table illustrates what has been stated.

b. **Spiritual Intelligence:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 2 (Appendix), which analyzes indicators (X6–X10) that measure the dimension of spiritual intelligence and the overall indicator, that the average (72.666%) of responses were at the level of (Strongly agree, Agree), while the other responses indicating disagreement were at a rate of (8.666%), and neutral responses were at (18.666%). These responses are supported by a mean value of (3.86) and a standard deviation of (0.898). The indicator that contributed to enriching the (positive) nature of this dimension is:

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of SPSS 28 statistical analysis program. (X9), which states "(Top management adopts a team-based work approach)," received an agreement rate of (83.333%). This rate is supported by a mean value of (4.133) and a standard deviation of (0.860), with a response rate of (82.666%), indicating cooperation and dedication in work among all members of the studied organization. The table illustrates what has been stated.

c. **Emotional Intelligence:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 3 (Appendix), which pertain to the analysis of indicators (X10–X15) measuring the dimension of emotional intelligence and the overall indicator, that an average of (53.333%) of the responses were in the categories of (strongly agree, agree), while the responses in disagreement accounted for (9.333%), and neutral responses constituted (37.333%). These responses are supported by a mean value of (3.64) and a standard deviation of (0.903). The indicator that contributed to enriching the (positive) aspect of this dimension is (X14), which states: “Senior management embraces critical situations without hesitation or resentment,” where the agreement rate for this indicator was (67%), supported by a mean value of (3.833) and a standard deviation of (0.874), with a response rate of (76.666%), indicating that senior management provides a supportive work environment with a cooperative spirit and without resentment. The table illustrates the aforementioned results.

2. Sustainable Performance

A. **Economic Dimension:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 4 (Appendix), related to the analysis of indicators (Y1–Y5) measuring the economic dimension and the overall indicator, that the average of (79.333%) of responses were in the categories (Strongly Agree, Agree). In contrast, the responses of disagreement accounted for (1.333%), and neutrality for (19.333%). These responses are supported by a mean value of (3.98) and a standard deviation of (0.643). The indicator that contributed to enriching the positivity of this dimension is (Y3), which states, “Top management works to strengthen its competitive position,” where the agreement percentage for this indicator was (90%). This rate is supported by a mean value of (4.233) and a standard deviation of (0.626), with a response rate of (84.666%), indicating that top management possesses the competitive advantage that makes it a leader in the work environment. The table illustrates what has been mentioned.

B. **Social Dimension:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 5 (Appendix), related to the analysis of indicators (Y6–Y10) measuring the social dimension and the overall indicator, that the average of (69.333%) of responses were in the categories (Strongly Agree, Agree). In contrast, the responses of disagreement accounted for (2.666%), and neutrality for (28%). These responses are supported by a mean value of (3.84) and a standard deviation of (0.746). The indicator that contributed to enriching the positivity of this dimension is (Y9), which states, “Top management supports charitable organizations within its scope of work,” where the agreement percentage for this indicator was (80%). This rate is supported by a mean value of (3.933) and a standard deviation of (0.583), with a response rate of (78.666%), indicating that top management views responsibility towards its community as one of its core pillars. The table illustrates what has been mentioned.

C. **Environmental Dimension:** It is evident from the percentages in Table 6 (Appendix), related to the analysis of indicators (Y11–Y15) measuring the environmental dimension and the overall indicator, that the average of (91.333%) of responses were in the categories (Strongly Agree, Agree). In contrast, the responses of disagreement accounted for (0%), and neutrality for (8.666%). These responses are supported by a mean value of (4.273) and a standard deviation of (0.593). The indicator that contributed to enriching the positivity of this dimension is (Y14), which states, “Top management sets guidelines to direct employee behavior in the area of energy consumption,” where the agreement percentage for this indicator was (93%). This rate is supported by a mean value of (4.466) and a standard deviation of (0.628), with a response rate of (89.333%), indicating that top management adopts sustainable environmental contributions in the field of energy. The table illustrates what has been mentioned.

Second: Correlation Relationships

This section focuses on the nature of the correlation relationships presented in the study model as follows:

1. Analysis of the Correlation Relationship Between the Variables of Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

The data in Table 7 reveal the nature of the correlation between the variable of smart leadership and sustainable performance. The value of the correlation coefficient between the two variables was (0.678), which is statistically significant, with a p-value of (0.000), which is much lower than the accepted margin of error (0.05). Accordingly, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no statistically significant correlation between smart leadership and sustainable performance” will be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis stating that “there is a statistically significant correlation between smart leadership and sustainable performance” will be accepted.

Table 7. Correlation Relationships Between the Study Variables

Correlation		Smart Leadership (X)
Sustainable Performance (Y)	Pearson Correlation	0.678**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	30

Source: Prepared by the researchers

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

2. Analysis of the Correlation Relationship Between the Dimensions of Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

The data in Table 8 reveal the nature of the correlation relationships between the dimensions of smart leadership and sustainable performance. The highest correlation coefficient value between the dimensions of smart leadership and sustainable performance was (0.698), which corresponds to emotional intelligence and is statistically significant, with a p-value of (0.000), which is far below the acceptable margin of error (0.05). The lowest value was for spiritual intelligence, recorded at (0.53). Accordingly, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and sustainable performance” will be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis stating that “there is a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and sustainable performance” will be accepted.

Table 8. Analysis of Correlation Relationships Between the Dimensions of Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

Correlation		Rational Intelligence	Spiritual Intelligence	Emotional Intelligence
Sustainable Performance (Y)	Pearson Correlation	.544**	.530**	.698**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.003	0
	N	30	30	30

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

3. Correlation Relationships Between the Dimensions of the Two Variables

The data in Table (9) reveal the nature of the correlation relationships between the dimensions of smart leadership and the dimensions of sustainable performance. The highest correlation

coefficient value between the dimensions of smart leadership and the dimensions of sustainable performance was (0.651), representing the correlation between emotional intelligence and the social dimension. This value is statistically significant, with a p-value of (0.000), which is much lower than the accepted margin of error (0.05). On the other hand, the lowest value was the correlation between spiritual intelligence and the environmental dimension, which was (0.014). Accordingly, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and the dimensions of sustainable performance” will be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis stating that “there is a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership and the dimensions of sustainable performance” will be accepted.

Table 9. Analysis of Correlation Relationships Between the Dimensions of Smart Leadership and the Dimensions of Sustainable Performance

Correlation		Rational Intelligence	Spiritual Intelligence	Emotional Intelligence
Economic Dimension	Pearson Correlation	0.341	.448*	.630**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.065	0.013	0
	N	30	30	30
Social Dimension	Pearson Correlation	.552**	.412*	.651**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.024	0
	N	30	30	30
Environmental Dimension	Pearson Correlation	.419*	.446*	.419*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.021	0.014	0.021
	N	30	30	30

Source: Prepared by the researchers

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Third: Impact Relationships

1. The Impact Relationship Between Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

The results in Table (10) indicate the impact of the variables smart leadership and sustainable performance, where the calculated F-value was (23.758). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was (0.459), indicating that 45.9% of the variance in smart leadership orientations is explained by sustainable performance. This is supported by a β value of (0.444) and a calculated T-value of (4.874), reflecting the respondents' perception of the ability to explain the impact of smart leadership on sustainable performance. Accordingly, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no statistically significant impact of smart leadership on sustainable performance” is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis stating that “there is a statistically significant impact of smart leadership on sustainable performance” is accepted.

Table 10. Analysis of the Impact Relationship Between Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	R Square	F	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	2.319	0.355	0.678	6.536	0.459	23.758	0.0068
Smart Leadership	0.444	0.091		4.874			0.005

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable Performance

2. The Impact Relationship Between the Dimensions of Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

The results in Table (11) indicate the impact of the dimensions of smart leadership on sustainable performance. The highest impact was for the emotional intelligence dimension, where the calculated F-value was (23.758). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was (0.487), indicating that 48.7% of the variance in emotional intelligence orientations is explained by sustainable performance. This is supported by a β value of (0.342) and a calculated T-value of (5.155), reflecting the respondents' ability to explain the effects of emotional intelligence on sustainable performance.

The lowest impact was for the spiritual intelligence dimension, where the calculated F-value was (10.966). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was (0.281), indicating that 28.1% of the variance in spiritual intelligence orientations is explained by sustainable performance. This is supported by a β value of (0.283) and a calculated T-value of (3.311), reflecting the respondents' ability to explain the effects of spiritual intelligence on sustainable performance.

Accordingly, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no statistically significant impact of the dimensions of smart leadership on sustainable performance" is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis stating that "there is a statistically significant impact of the dimensions of smart leadership on sustainable performance" is accepted.

Table 11. Analysis of the Impact Relationship Between the Dimensions of Smart Leadership and Sustainable Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	R Square	F	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	2.275	0.515	0.544	4.415	0.295	11.741	0.0012
	Rational Intelligence	0.432	0.126		3.426			0.005
2	(Constant)	2.937	0.335	0.53	8.761	0.281	10.966	0.0023
	Spiritual Intelligence	0.283	0.086		3.311			0.005
3	(Constant)	2.785	0.246	0.698	11.305	0.487	26.579	0.0054
	Emotional Intelligence	0.342	0.066		5.155			0.005

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable Performance

Results and Discussion

The results indicate a significant correlation between smart leadership and sustainable performance at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh. This reflects that applying the principles of smart leadership enhances the continuity of performance and the efficiency of achieving the organization's goals. Key elements such as strategic thinking, adaptive decision-making, and interaction with environmental changes emerge as main factors supporting long-term organizational sustainability.

The results show a statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of smart leadership (rational, emotional, and spiritual intelligence) and sustainable performance at the Technical

Management Institute in Nineveh. This demonstrates that activating these integrated dimensions contributes to achieving stability and high efficiency in organizational performance. Rational intelligence supports thinking and decision-making, emotional intelligence enhances understanding of others' feelings, and spiritual intelligence nourishes values and meaning in work, thereby achieving performance sustainability at both individual and organizational levels.

The study results indicate a significant impact of smart leadership in enhancing sustainable performance at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh. This suggests that adopting smart leadership styles with their rational, emotional, and spiritual capabilities contributes to improving efficiency, continuity, and quality. The impact goes beyond daily behaviors to form a strategic foundation for sustainability. Smart leadership contributes to adapting to changes, stimulating creativity, and strengthening organizational values.

The study showed a statistically significant impact of the dimensions of smart leadership (rational, emotional, and spiritual intelligence) in achieving sustainable performance. This indicates that the integration of these leadership dimensions is a decisive factor in supporting performance continuity and achieving the strategic goals of the organization in a complex and changing work environment.

The study revealed a statistically significant impact of the dimensions of smart leadership (rational, emotional, and spiritual) on enhancing sustainable performance. This indicates that the integration of these dimensions effectively supports the continuity of performance and the efficient and flexible achievement of organizational goals in changing work environments.

Both innovation and flexibility in smart leadership contribute to facing challenges and achieving organizational excellence at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh. This suggests that leaders with the ability to innovate and quickly adapt to changes enhance the organization's readiness and ability to deal with difficult circumstances, positively reflecting on its performance level and sustained success.

Supporting smart leadership within a flexible organizational environment and participatory culture contributes to enhancing the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh's ability to achieve its long-term goals. This integration promotes teamwork spirit, stimulates innovation, and improves responsiveness to changes, which positively affects the sustainability of organizational performance.

Conclusions

Design, implement, and develop training programs aimed at developing smart leadership skills among academic and administrative leaders at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

Increase the integration of technology in administrative and educational processes to achieve efficiency and sustainability in performance at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

Encourage a culture of innovation within the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh by supporting new initiatives and ideas from students and staff members.

Activate organizational participation by involving individuals and students in decision-making and strategic planning at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

To enhance the concepts of smart leadership, it is recommended to intensify training programs and workshops that introduce academic leaders to smart leadership concepts, skills in using technology for decision-making, and effective communication at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

Activate a performance evaluation system based on smart criteria by establishing an evaluation system grounded on digital and intelligent standards, linked to sustainability and organizational quality goals at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

It is necessary to incorporate smart leadership principles into strategic plans due to their direct impact on enhancing sustainable organizational performance at the Technical Management Institute in Nineveh.

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Appendix

Table 1. Description and Diagnosis of Rational Intelligence

Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree					
	5-		-4		-3		-2		-1					
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%				
X1	10	33.3	17	56.7	3	10.0					4.2333	.62606	14.7888736	84.6666667
X2	4	13.3	21	70.0	4	13.3	1	3.3			3.9333	.63968	16.2631482	78.6666667
X3	9	30.0	14	46.7	6	20.0	1	3.3			4.0333	.80872	20.0508317	80.6666667
X4	9	30.0	18	60.0	2	6.7	1	3.3			4.1667	.69893	16.7743647	83.3333333
X5	5	16.7	18	60.0	7	23.3					3.9333	.63968	16.2631482	78.6666667
Overall Mean	24.66666667		58.66666667		14.66666667		3.333333333		0		4.0600	0.6826	16.8281	81.2000

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Table 2. Description and Diagnosis of Spiritual Intelligence

Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree					
	5-		-4		-3		-2		-1					
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%				
X6	3	10.0	17	56.7	5	16.7	5	16.7			3.6000	.89443	24.8451997	72
X7	6	20.0	17	56.7	5	16.7	2	6.7			3.9000	.80301	20.5900403	78
X8	7	23.3	12	40.0	10	33.3			1	3.3	3.8000	.92476	24.3356665	76
X9	11	36.7	14	46.7	3	10.0	2	6.7			4.1333	.86037	20.8153097	82.6666667
X10	8	26.7	14	46.7	5	16.7	2	6.7	1	3.3	3.8667	1.00801	26.0693241	77.3333333
Overall Mean	23.33333333		49.33333333		18.66666667		7.333		1.3333		3.8600	0.8981	23.3311	77.2000
Total	72.66666667				8.666									

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program.

Table 3. Description and Diagnosis of Emotional Intelligence

Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)	
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree						
	5-		-4		-3		-2		-1						
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%					
X11	6	20.0	9	30.0	13	43.3	2	6.7			3.6333	.88992	24.4931556	72.6666667	
X12	2	6.7	12	40.0	14	46.7	2	6.7			3.4667	.73030	21.0662522	69.3333333	
X13	6	20.0	8	26.7	12	40.0	4	13.3			3.5333	.97320	27.5435154	70.6666667	
X14	7	23.3	13	43.3	8	26.7	2	6.7			3.8333	.87428	22.8073386	76.6666667	
X15	9	30.0	8	26.7	9	30.0	4	13.3			3.7333	1.04826	28.0784126	74.6666667	
Overall Mean	20		33.33333333		37.33333333		9.333333333		0		3.6400	0.9032	24.7977	72.8000	
Total	53.33333333										9.333333333				

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Table 4. Description and Diagnosis of the Economic Dimension

Economic Dimension														
Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree					
	5-		-4		-3		-2		-1					
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%				
Y1	1	3.3	21	70.0	8	26.7					3.7667	.50401	13.380715	75.3333333
Y2	7	23.3	12	40.0	10	33.3	1	3.3			3.8333	.83391	21.7541178	76.6666667
Y3	10	33.3	17	56.7	3	10.0					4.2333	.62606	14.7888736	84.6666667
Y4	4	13.3	20	66.7	5	16.7	1	3.3			3.9000	.66176	16.9682969	78
Y5	8	26.7	19	63.3	3	10.0					4.1667	.59209	14.210244	83.3333333
Overall Mean	20		59.33333333		19.33333333		1.33333333		0		3.9800	0.6436	16.2204	79.6000
Total	79.33333333						1.33333333							

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Table 5. Description and Diagnosis of the Social Dimension

Social Dimension														
Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree					
	5-		-4		-3		-2		-1					
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%				
Y6	8	26.7	15	50.0	5	16.7	1	3.3	1	3.3	3.9333	.94443	24.0110129	78.6666667
Y7	3	10.0	21	70.0	6	20.0					3.9000	.54772	14.0441681	78
Y8	8	26.7	8	26.7	13	43.3	1	3.3			3.7667	.89763	23.830996	75.3333333
Y9	4	13.3	20	66.7	6	20.0					3.9333	.58329	14.8294648	78.6666667
Y10	4	13.3	13	43.3	12	40.0	1	3.3			3.6667	.75810	20.6754012	73.3333333
Overall Mean	18		51.33333333		28		2		0.666666667		3.8400	0.7462	19.4782	76.8000
Total	69.33333333				2.666666667									

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

Table 6. Description and Diagnosis of the Environmental Dimension

Environmental Dimension														
Items	Response Scale										Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Response Percentage (%)
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree					
	5-		4		3		2		1					
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%				
Y11	8	26.7	17	56.7	5	16.7					4.1000	.66176	16.1405751	82
Y12	5	16.7	21	70.0	4	13.3					4.0333	.55605	13.7864483	80.6666667
Y13	13	43.3	16	53.3	1	3.3					4.4000	.56324	12.8009511	88
Y14	16	53.3	12	40.0	2	6.7					4.4667	.62881	14.0778409	89.3333333
Y15	12	40.0	17	56.7	1	3.3					4.3667	.55605	12.7340477	87.3333333
Overall Mean	36		55.33333333		8.666666667		0		0		4.2733	0.5932	13.9080	85.4667
Total	91.33333333						0							

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS 28 statistical analysis program

